

based on the number of lesions, were recorded at 45 days after seeding: less than 1% lesions, highly resistant; 1–576 lesions, moderately resistant; 5–25% lesions, intermediate; 25–50% lesions, moderately susceptible; and more than 50% lesions, highly susceptible.

Only 8 percent were resistant to brown spot and 4 percent to narrow leaf spot. The lines that were resistant to both diseases are shown in the accompanying table. RD1 and Khao Dawk Mali 105 were classified as intermediate and moderately susceptible, respectively. Infection of brown spot fungus was severe at both the Kuan Gut and the Ubolrajthani Rice Experiment Stations, but narrow leaf spot infection was severe only at Kuan Gut.

Direct and indirect effect of Udbatta disease on total number of panicles per hill in different paddy cultures

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Udbatta disease caused by *Ephelis oryzae* Syd. is one of the important paddy diseases in Karnataka. Affected plants show profuse tillering early in plant growth, whitening of young leaves, nonproductive panicles, panicles in the form of cylindrical rods, or a few diseased and healthy panicles in the same clump. Reporting on the direct loss from the disease, Shivanandappa said that wherever the primary tiller was infected, the percentage of infection within the hill ranged from 20 to 95 percent. But when infection took place on the secondary and tertiary tillers, the percentage of diseased panicles varied from 13 to 55 percent. The indirect loss from the disease in terms of reduction in total number of productive panicles in the affected hill is not known. Hence the following study was conducted.

Twenty short- and 20 medium-duration rices were selected and sown in kharif 1974 at Mandya in randomized block

Effect of Udbatta disease on the total number of panicles per hill. Rice Research Station, Mandya, and Department of Plant Pathology, UAS, Hebbal, Bangalore, India.

Variety or culture	Disease incidence (%)	Healthy panicles (no.)		Panicles per diseased hill (no.)	Diseased panicles (no.)		
		Per healthy hill	Per diseased hill		Per diseased hill	Indirectly lost	Total lost
<i>Shortduration cultures</i>							
MR 118	8.25	10.52	7.64	9.89	2.25	0.63	2.88
MR 263	4.24	12.02	8.33	10.02	1.69	2.00	3.69
MR 272	4.76	14.08	10.68	12.12	1.44	1.96	3.40
MR 279	4.54	13.28	11.52	12.92	1.40	0.36	1.76
MR 297	5.60	8.56	6.45	8.26	1.81	0.30	2.11
MR 298	5.21	9.60	7.32	9.21	1.89	0.39	2.28
MR 299	4.96	9.41	6.96	8.64	1.68	0.77	2.45
MR 300	2.41	8.88	6.12	7.77	1.65	1.11	2.76
MR 301	4.96	10.41	7.94	9.83	1.89	0.58	2.47
MR 318	2.44	8.77	6.12	8.02	1.90	0.75	2.65
IET 1522	3.89	9.45	6.04	7.82	1.78	1.63	3.41
IET 1899	2.06	10.26	6.60	8.29	1.69	1.97	3.66
IET 1988	2.73	10.73	8.52	10.13	1.61	0.60	2.21
IET 2246	2.93	8.77	6.37	7.87	1.50	0.90	2.40
IET 2386	2.28	11.25	8.26	9.86	1.60	1.39	2.99
IET 2671	3.94	9.64	6.85	8.55	1.70	1.09	2.79
IET 2707	3.44	10.50	8.30	10.20	1.90	0.30	2.20
IET 2968	4.60	11.20	7.73	9.53	1.80	1.67	3.47
IET 3126	4.99	10.85	7.80	9.80	2.00	1.05	3.05
Madhu	4.70	11.29	8.42	10.38	1.96	0.91	2.87
<i>Medium-duration cultures</i>							
MR 44	6.30	14.85	11.96	14.29	2.33	0.56	2.89
MR 70	5.06	14.26	11.28	13.34	2.06	0.92	2.98
MR 81	5.00	12.80	10.37	12.44	2.07	0.36	2.43
MR 249	4.38	14.80	12.70	14.40	1.70	0.40	2.10
MR 269	3.84	11.60	9.11	10.99	1.88	0.61	2.49
GMR 2	4.76	11.01	7.43	9.38	1.95	1.63	3.58
Satya	3.60	11.16	7.78	9.54	1.76	1.62	3.38
Surya	3.53	12.36	10.11	11.86	1.75	0.50	2.25
Suhasini	5.17	12.20	8.65	10.83	2.18	1.37	3.55
Jaya	4.69	11.45	8.46	10.57	2.11	0.88	2.99
IR20	4.18	11.73	9.08	11.14	2.06	0.59	2.65
J.H. 49	3.53	8.85	6.68	8.36	1.68	0.49	2.17
IET 1990	4.31	11.65	8.60	10.53	1.93	1.12	3.05
IET 1991	3.26	11.58	8.88	10.83	1.95	0.75	2.91
IET 2142	4.69	11.36	8.45	10.61	2.16	0.75	2.91
IET 2143	3.80	13.83	11.41	13.19	1.78	0.64	2.42
IET 2254	3.87	12.46	9.86	11.79	1.93	0.67	2.60
IET 2295	2.92	14.60	12.85	14.36	1.51	0.24	1.75
IET 2300	6.15	11.73	8.36	10.27	1.91	1.46	3.37
IET 2384	3.87	13.55	10.56	12.39	1.83	1.16	2.99

design with three replications. Twenty-five healthy and diseased hills of each culture were randomly selected in each replication. The healthy and diseased panicles at grain formation in healthy and diseased hills were counted. The number of diseased panicles in diseased hills (direct loss) was obtained by counting the affected panicles in each diseased hill. The indirect loss of panicles was obtained by deducting the total number of panicles (healthy and diseased) in diseased hills from the total number of healthy panicles in healthy

hills. The total loss of panicles was calculated as both direct and indirect loss (see table).

The percentage of disease incidence varied from culture to culture. There was no correlation between the percentage of incidence and the direct or indirect loss of panicles. The range of indirect loss of panicles from culture to culture varied greatly. The number of directly lost panicles per hill ranged from 1.40 to 2.33; that of the indirectly lost ranged from 0.3 to 2.00. Total lost panicles ranged from 1.75 to 3.69.